

Research

Multi-Dimensional Approaches of National Policy on Disaster Management in Action in Sri Lanka

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Abstract: *On account of climate change, global warming, and rapid and growing urbanization, human civilizations are mostly experiencing disasters. Of late, one of the critical South Asian countries- Sri Lanka has achieved almost all aspects development, but unfortunately, the achievements of the country are fading due to the disasters. The catastrophic Tsunami of 2004 obligates the concerning authorities of Sri Lanka to rethink about the disaster management and disaster resilience. As an effective measure and operational instrument soon after Tsunami, in 2005 Sri Lankan government has adopted Disaster Management Act and, later on in 2010 formulated the National Policy of Disaster Management to integrate all Government, non-government, private, civil society and international communities.*

This present has focused on the congeniality of multi-dimensional national disaster management policy is implementing disaster risk reduction operations in Sri Lanka by multiple cases of actual disasters have stroked earlier.

Keywords: *Disaster resilience; national policy; multi-dimensions; policy actions; multi-stakeholders; multi-sectors; multi-phases*

Introduction

Sri Lanka is a small island state in the Indian Ocean with the former name "Ceylon". The total size of the island state is 65610 km², with 1700 km kilometers long coastal region (Koralagama, D., 2008). This tiny island state is situated at the southeastern zone of the Indian Ocean and remains disaster-prone around the year, having two types of monsoon wind (MoDM, Sri Lanka, 2018). Flood due to heavy monsoon rain, downward pressure, drought due to lack of monsoon rain sometimes are the most frequent natural disasters. Besides these, landslides, thunderstorms, coastal region erosion, environmental pollution, tsunami, cyclones are also struck on Sri Lanka

regularly (MoDM, Sri Lanka 2018). In almost every year Sri Lanka is affected by the flood on two occasions along with landslides, drought, storm, thunderstorms etc. In light of the discovery of the disaster's history of Sri Lanka, we have found that this South Asian tiny country is located dangerously within two fault lines of the Indian Ocean and the Bay of Bengal (Tamil Canadian, 2004). Sri Lanka's warm and tropical weather brings heavy rainfall in the summer. Though it has a vast river channel with heavy rainfall, it fails to accommodate all the drainage water. However, mainland Sri Lanka has surrounded by a prolonged river channel. The 335 kilometers long Mahaweli River is the longest river in Sri Lanka, which is originated from Polwathura, Mahaweli area and took the merge with the Bay of Bengal after connecting one-fifth of the mainland of Sri Lanka (Rivers Network, 2018). Also, Sri Lanka has a total of 103 rivers, including Malvathu, Kala Oye, Kelani, Yan Oya, Dedura Oya have strengthened and enriched the drainage system of Sri Lanka. But due to the extreme heat wave in summer, the influence of monsoon and the monsoon wind encounter with the slopes of central highland, it causes heavy rainfall. This excessive heavy rainfall causes the flood in Sri Lanka; therefore, the central concern of the disaster management authority of Sri Lanka remains within the hilly declivity and flood. Besides the flood, landslides, thunderstorms, coastal region erosion, tsunami, cyclone etc. agitate Sri Lanka throughout the year (World Population Review, 2013). The country has experienced the worse hit by the Tsunami in 2004, which caused the death of over 35000 people (ABC.NET, 2014). The trend of flood in Sri Lanka is changing for the last ten years enormously. Fifty percent private sectors in all spheres of the economic cycle got affected by the flood in 2010. Tropical storm Roanu caused flood along with landslides of 22 districts in Sri Lanka in May 2016. Hydro metrological hazards are increasing since Sri Lanka is one of the worse victims of climate change in the world. Due to this new alarming concept, major flooding events occurred in 2010, 2011, 2014, 2016 and 2017. The total expenditure of the Ministry of Disaster Management has estimated RS 690 million due to the flood event in the year of 2016 in Sri Lanka. In the course of 2007-2011, the local and central government expenditure for the overall mitigation and rehabilitation process caused by disasters had exceeded RS. 1.7 billion (Talking Economics, 2017).

To secure the disaster-prone Sri Lanka, the Government is working with non-government, development organizations and other stakeholders continuously. The Sri Lankan Government has taken several legal measures to ensure effective disaster management. Among these, the

National Policy on Disaster Management, which was approved by the National Council for Disaster Management on December 28, 2010, is notable. (NPDM, 2010). The aim of the present study is to explore the congeniality of multi-dimensional approaches of disaster management policy to manage the disasters effectively throughout multiple time period, multiple stakeholders, multi-sectorial and locality with the insurance of disaster resilience fostering the culture of safety during a disaster in Sri Lanka.

Literature Review

The vision and objective of the policy is to protect Sri Lanka from disasters, and this protection includes the people, property and the environment. Considering as the core concept of disaster management in Sri Lanka, the National Council for Disaster Management approved the National Policy on Disaster Management on 28.12.2010. The Policy was all about effective disaster management and building resilience with the participation of all stakeholders. Sri Lanka has experienced the inadequacies during the devastating Tsunami 2004. The concerning authorities have identified some major management problems, i.e., coordination amongst the stakeholder agencies, duplication of the efforts in same places, insufficient policy directives, and so on. Though the parliamentarian committee recommended for the formulation of the national Policy because of some fundamental and necessary background tasks, it took a few couple years to finally approved.

Meanwhile, the Disaster Management Act was in action in the year of 2005. With the policy guideline by the council and coordination through the act, the Policy was finally approved in 2010. The policy was developed from a road map of disaster management from 2006 to 2016; a road map for DM was finalized with the major 60 outcomes in Sri Lanka. This road map is one of the basics of the policy which is deeply rooted in the guidance from DM act. The policy makes the National Disaster Management Plan (NDMP); National Emergency Operations Plan; Disaster Management Plans for every Ministry, Government Department and public corporation; and other plans, programs and guidelines functional with the policy suggested the mechanism of operations and rearing up the culture of safety.

The objective of the Study

This current examines the multi-dimensional national policy on disaster management in Sri Lanka in precautionary phase and how it works while disaster to minimize the loss of life and property and how it ensures the rehabilitation process shortly after any course of disaster.

Significance of the Study

The significant finding/s of this present study will aid the disaster resilience within the legal framework of Sri Lanka in all management phases. For the disaster-prone nations, it is the prerequisite to activate all races of the society to ensure resilience. To activate and energize the overall resilience legal framework for the management is a mandatory feature because, without the specific policy, it is difficult to ensure sustainable management and resilience as well. Thus every disaster concern and prone nation approves and adopt the laws and policies. Sometimes these work for regional and sometimes for the overall nation. Being aversively experienced by the disasters, the Government of Sri Lanka has approved and adopted the Disaster Management Act in 2005 and followed by the National Policy on Disaster Management in 2010. The policies has emerged because of the inadequate coordination amongst the stakeholder's agencies, replication of good practices and avoid the duplication of efforts in the same field and provide a legal baseline to ensure collective efforts for reducing the overall losses. The National Policy on Disaster Management 2010 is the key-driven force to rear the culture of safety, so it has evolved with the multi-dimensional approaches and applications. This present Study believes that the multi-dimensional applications of the esteemed policy and the real application of that will aid sustainable disaster management actions.

Methodology

This present study explores the applicability of the National Policy on Disaster Management through a multi-dimensional approach for managing disasters in pre-during and post phases. The study has employed secondary sources of data to explore all possible matters of disaster management in Sri Lanka i.e. Disaster Management Ministry, Government and non-government reports regarding disaster management Law and Act, online data bank, books, journals and other relevant documents to make the overall conception comprehensive. The concerning authority of Sri Lanka has taken the national policy as an effective tool for managing disasters effectively, so the legislation is the prime concern for this present research since the legislative matter is the main concern of this present study so the research is qualitative and ended up with some directions and recommendations.

Study Design

Since data was collected from secondary sources, and dealt with the quantitative assumptions with analysis, so it was preferred the quantitative research design best suit here.

Discussion

The objective of this present Study was to investigate the multi-dimensional features of the National Policy of Disaster Management of Sri Lanka to ensure effective disaster management there. To explore the matter above, we have chosen the research design with the combination of both quantitative and qualitative assumptions through the access of the primary and secondary sources. National Policy on Disaster Management (2010) is a comprehensive tool to create a resilient community. The policy is increasing the culture of safety through its multi-dimensional approaches. The policy has included multi hazards, including natural, human-induced and technological destructions. Different but absolute phases of disaster management have been covered by this policy where prevention, reduction, mitigation, preparedness, emergency operations, relief, recovery, rehabilitation and reconstruction and review have been addressed. Concerning the sectors, the policy has integrated the government sectors to ensure effective disaster management, i.e. emergency services, meteorology, human and social services, infrastructure, education and training, health, agriculture, defense, water management, environment, climate change, urban management and relevant others. This policy believes in the active participation and engagement of all stakeholders', i.e. national public agencies, the private sector, civil society, the international community and the general public towards the same goal. The multi-locality concept of the policy engages the international, regional and national efforts covering the entire territory of Sri Lanka, i.e. land, sea and air. The final simultaneous sector is based on the period, the multi-temporal concept, which includes the short, medium and long term plan and preparation. One important matter to be noted here that, all these multifunction's are concerning to protect the human, property and the environment of Sri Lanka from the grief of disaster/s.

Figure:1 Multi-Dimensional Cycle of the National Policy on Disaster Management

As the study focuses on the multi-dimensional disaster readiness through the national policy so it investigates 2 cases after the approval of the policy in 2010:

Case 1: Flood and Landslides 2017

Brief History

Sri Lanka is being affected with the southwestern monsoons around the year because the monsoon causes heavy rain which followed by flood and subsequent landslides. The situation got worst in 2017 which started on 18-19 May 2019 (Wikipedia, 2018). Two simultaneous matters made the overall situation worsen. In one hand with the arrival of precursor system to Cyclone Mora, affected Sri Lanka with flood and landslides in the end of the May 2017 and the drought in the near past accelerate the neoteric development of flood with frequent landslides and flash flood. As of late, more than 700000 people got affected with the death over 200 people (IOM, 2017).

Table-1: Record of Loss and Damage of the Flood and Landslides 2017

Loss or Damage	Amount/ Number	Costs/ specification
Affected the life and living of the local people	698,289	
Dead	208	
No. of missing persons	95	
Total number of Districts affected	15	
Worse affected Districts	04	Kalutara, Matara, Galle and Ratnapura
Families Affected	175,660	
Houses Destroyed	2,545 Houses	
Damaged	15,897	
In Evacuation Centres	21,681	
Estimated Total Economic loss	\$200 Million	

Source: IOM & Wikipedia, 2017

Example of Multi-Dimensional Approach or Not

Multi-Hazard

There are no reported multi-hazard issues for the flood and landslides in 2017. No case of man-made and technological hazards was found while analyzing the background. The flood got worsens because of the monsoons and the previous drought. Although it was bound only into the natural hazard but the devastation was multi phasic. The flood affected about 700000 people of 15 districts and the death toll was highest after the approval of the national policy on disaster management because of flood and landslide. But the authority was prepared for coping with any case of such.

Multi-Phasic

We have found some very basic problems in preparatory phase. For this particular reason we might address the ministry of disaster management responsible. The evacuation was not so smooth in the worse affected regions. People needed emergency shelter those who have lost their house completely. Local schools and temples were used as the shelter house for them but because of the lack in preparedness the people suffered a lot specially they have slept in floor, lack in toilet, food, drinking water and especially for the breast feeding mother was beyond imagination. It took long time to recover the electricity. But overall relief and rehabilitation process was satisfactory in terms of the willingness of different authorities. But we have experienced extreme lack in alert the people for reducing the loss of property and life.

Multi-Sectorial

In this event of disaster we have seen some collective of efforts of the offices from Sri Lankan authority. But we have seen lack in early warning period. But soon after the flood the different offices and forces collectively started recovery operations and rehabilitation programs. The operations in brief are:

- For the medical operations, at first the mobile health units were deployed while evacuation and shelters.
- Local authority ensured the temporary shelter at the local schools and temples.

- Soon after the flood started, the National Building Research Organization (NBRO) issued the landslide warning.
- Different departments of Sri Lankan Army i.e. Commando, Special Forces, Mechanized Infantry and Army medical personnel. BTRs, WMZs troop carriers and 30 Army boats and other machinery were deployed with 1700 personnel for that disaster management.
- 110 search and rescue teams consisted 776 naval personnel with 116 boats were involved for management.
- Sri Lankan Air Force deployed their aircrafts for reconnaissance and relief operations.
- Overall 77000 people were evacuated most with the operations of Sri Lankan military forces.

These efforts proved the effective multi-sectional operations in the post disaster operations.

Multi-Stakeholders & Multi-Locality

The National Policy on Disaster Management of Sri Lanka believes in the active involvement of all national agencies, private sectors, civil society and international community together in different periods of disaster management. In our case no. 1 we have seen the operations from different sectors as like:

- The search-rescue and evacuation operations started over 10000 military personnel of Sri Lanka deployed collectively through land, air and sea regime.
- Humanitarian Country Team initiated the development of an in-country emergency response plan.
- International Organization for Migration (IOM) initiated the evacuation operations.
- Ministry of Health Offices, District Secretariats initiated the mobile medical team to provide medical support in evacuation and shelters.
- Landslide warning alerts have been issued by the National Building Research Organization (NBRO) in a number of Divisions.
- Foreign Minister told "16 countries had rushed relief supplies and medicine
- During the flood of 2017, we have seen the direct search and rescue operation, relief program and medical camps conducted by the military and civilian authorities of India,

China, USA, Singapore, UK, Pakistan, Australia, Israel, Maldives, Korea and others. The outcomes of the international cooperation is as following:

Table-2: International Assistance for the Flood and Landslides 2017

Country	Assistance	Unit/ Amount
India	Rescue, diving and medical & relief.	40 tons of relief materials
China	Relief & Medical operations.	US\$2.2 million's relief goods.
USA	Post-flood recovery operations, humanitarian assistance operations.	US\$2.3 million cash.
Singapore	Cash contribution and relief operations.	US\$100,000 cash & US\$50,000 relief goods
UK	Relief	Unknown
Pakistan	Relief and medical operations.	Unknown
Australia	Search and rescue operations, relief.	AUD \$500,000
Israel	Relief operation.	Unknown
Maldives	Cash contribution and relief operations.	US\$250,000 cash
Korea	Cash contribution and relief operations.	US\$250,000 cash

Source: Wikipedia, 2018

Multi-Temporal

Though the National Policy on Disaster Management has focused on the multi-temporal matter as an important one but we have seen, for the case of the flood of 2017, the multi-temporal concept was absent there. We have seen the short and medium term operations but mostly medium term and in the post disaster management. The preparedness was quite unsatisfactory. The evacuation, shelter, food, immediate medical operations was not successful completely. We have seen the collective measures from different offices and military forces of Sri Lanka along with the active participation of military and non-military personnel of 16 different countries and also some local and international organizations like Red Cross, Sarvodaya and Foundation of Goodness. So the policy was not successful properly in this concept of multi-temporal planning and preparedness phase.

Case 2: Flood and Landslides 2016

Brief History

As we have mentioned earlier that, Sri Lanka is being affected with the southwestern monsoons around the year and that was not exceptional for the year 2016 as well. The flood of 2016 started on May 14 when a low pressure area over the Bay of Bengal caused torrential rain to fall across Sri Lanka, causing floods and landslides and ultimately which affected more than half a million people there.

Table-3: Record of Loss and Damage of the Flood and Landslides 2016

Loss or Damage	Amount/ Number	Costs/ specification
Affected the life and living of the local people	500,000 (Appx.)	
Dead	101	
No. of missing persons	100	
Total number of Districts affected	22	
Worse affected Districts	10	Chilaw, Colombo, Galle, Kalutara, Kandy, Kegalle, Matara, Nuwara

		Eliya and Ratnapura.
Forced Migration	223,687	
Houses Destroyed	230	
Damaged	2647	
Relief Centres	357	
Estimated Total Economic loss	\$2 Billion	

Source: IOM & Wikipedia, 2016

Multi-Hazard

Although the flood of 2016 was associated with the landslides but that was only concentrated into the natural disasters. There was no presence of man-made or technological disasters involved. Since Sri Lanka is not a techno-giant so there will be always less chance to have the technological disasters along with the natural one. But the natural disasters got some multi dimensions like the recovery issue, medical, educational, rehabilitation, water and sewerage and safety issue as well.

Multi-Phasic

The basic problems were there in the preparatory phase and we did expect that will be ensured in future but in real that was not done properly so the same thing happened in the year 2017. Emergency evacuation, shelter, medical, privacy, rehabilitation in all of these there were problems. So the loss of life, property and environment was enormous. Most pathetic matter was some 100 people was missing and remain the same till now.

Multi-Sectorial

With the lack in the early alarm phase, the collective operations of different offices, forces and organizations are as:

- For the medical operations, at first the mobile health units were deployed while evacuation and shelters.
- Local authority ensured the temporary shelter at the local schools and temples.

- The Sri Lanka Army deployed more than 1500 Army personnel for search and rescue and relief operations.
- Sri Lankan air force has deployed their helicopters for rescue operations and providing of relief aid to victims.
- The Sri Lanka Navy dispatched 81 flood relief teams.

These efforts proved the effective multi-sectional operations in the post disaster operations.

Multi-Stakeholders & Multi-Locality

The willingness was proper but because of resource constraints the authority of Sri Lanka urged international support to tackle the flood in the year of 2016.

- With the collective efforts by thousands of military personnel on Sri Lanka, the post disaster operations started in all three land, water and air regime.
- Ministry of Disaster Management immediately stated the recovery program in worse affected areas.
- Several offices and organizations started the evaluation process immediately to arrange the relief properly.
- Medicine, drinking water and sewerage system was taken into the consideration very seriously.
- During the flood of 2016 the international cooperation was like as following:

Table-4: International Assistance for the Flood and Landslides 2017

Country	Assistance	Unit/ Amount
Commonwealth Nations	Condolences by the Secretary General.	
USA	Post-flood recovery operations, humanitarian assistance operations	\$1000000
Singapore	Relief operations.	\$150,000
Pakistan	Relief and medical	30 Bed's hospital

	operations.	
Australia	Clean water and sanitation for children in shelters.	AUD \$500,000
Nepal	Relief operation.	\$100,000
Japan	blankets, generators, water purifiers and water tanks	Unknown
India	Humanitarian assistances.	Unknown

Source: Wikipedia, 2018

Multi-Temporal

Again the preparatory phase was disappointing than the recovery operations. In this course of disaster more than 10 countries and international organizations worked together for mitigating the problems made with this flood of 2016. But the actual time based operation was absent there.

Conclusion & Recommendations

Sri Lankan National Policy on Disaster Management is the core legal tool for disaster management, which is directing the stakeholders to minimize the damage and fostering the culture of safety through resilience. The Policy is intended to integrate other core public components, i.e. National Disaster Management Plan, National Emergency Operations Plan, Disaster Management Plan of every ministry and 'Government's departments and public cooperation. The Policy itself a high-level operation manual of 'how things should be' to ensure resilience. Considering the protection of life and property, it guides the preparedness, prevention and response after the course of disasters where public awareness and capacity building work simultaneously. This present study focuses on the multi-dimensional aspects of the national policy 2010. The policy addresses the multi-hazards where natural, human-induced and technological hazards are being considered. With before, during and after disaster management operations, the multi-phases have also been addressed where prevention, reduction, preparedness, emergency relief, recovery and rehabilitation have been considered. Multi-sectors of the policy integrates the different service delivery departments, emergency services, health,

education, agriculture and relevant all parties. Conceptualizing disaster management, multi-stakeholders i.e. national agencies, private and civil society and the international community, are being integrated. The multi-locality aspect of the policy combines the efforts of international, regional and national levels. The policy is also focuses on the multi-temporal operations to build capacity, in a short, mid and long term basis. The effort made for formalizing the policy is enormous in terms of disaster management where previous lacking and mistakes are being considered significantly.

After having a clear conception about the disasters and the role of the national policy, this study is recommending:

- The policy must describe how the relevant agency/person will act according to the different types of hazards, i.e. natural, human-induced and technological disasters.
- It is good to know that different phases of management have been addressed by the policy very well, but for disaster, prevention measures should be taken more seriously than that of the recovery and rehabilitation phase so that the amount of damage could be minimized.
- Integration of different offices amongst the Government should be more transparent and responsible.
- Combing the efforts of all stakeholders is must make the Policy successful and ensure effective disaster management as well.
- Disaster has no political or economic border, so international, regional and national efforts should be mobilized effectively.
- According to the perspective, multi-temporal plans and preparedness should be taken carefully.
- To ensure the real culture of safety in Sri Lanka through this National Policy on Disaster Management.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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